

PRODUCTIVITY OF AGRICULTURAL CROPS DEPENDING ON THE METHODS OF SOIL TILLAGE IN THE CONDITIONS OF POLISSYA OF UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

One of the key tasks of modern agriculture is effective management of the soil ecosystem, preventing the spread of soil degradation processes and preserving its energy potential. In this sense, the aim of the study was to study the possibility of improving the main agrophysical and hydro-physical indicators of the arable layer of light gray forest soil as a component of managing the fertility of light soils in Polesya and the formation of productive agrocenosis.

Keywords: density of addition of the soil, soil porosity, crop yields, agrotechnology, light gray forest soils.

Problem statement. The progressive deterioration of the qualitative state of agro-landscapes in Ukraine, the decline in soil fertility create real prerequisites for further aggravation of the crisis of agricultural production and organic food [1]. In the current conditions in Ukraine, the problem of reducing anthropogenic pressure on the agroecosystem, which negatively affects the reproduction of soil fertility in the process of its intensive agricultural use, in particular in Polesie, is of particular importance.

Scientific literature widely reflects various aspects of the influence of tillage and fertilisation methods on agrophysical soil parameters and their impact on crop productivity [3, 6, 8]. However, some of them are contradictory in nature. Thus, our studies prove the advantage of shallow no-tillage main tillage and alternative fertiliser systems in improving soil agrophysical indicators [5]. However, some researchers indicate a decrease in water holding capacity on the backgrounds where shallow tillage was applied, justifying such changes by increasing soil density [2, 7]. Some authors note that changes in soil density do not directly affect root development, but affect pore location and structure, soil strength, total porosity, number of large pores, volumetric water content, water permeability and soil aeration [9]. Each of these indirect effects of changes in soil density can have a direct effect on root development. Others point to the retardation of root growth under shallow tillage, which is due to the deterioration of the water and air regime, in particular a sharp reduction in available moisture reserves [4]. The authors emphasise that insufficient intensity of loosening can lead to the occurrence of critical levels of soil physical properties and disturbance of growth and development of plant root systems. In addition, deterioration of agrophysical parameters (overconsolidation) and overwatering worsen soil microbiological activity and aggravate unproductive N losses [10, 11]. In this regard, the study of the impact of biologisation elements of agrotechnologies on agrophysical and water-physical indi-

cators in specific soil-climatic conditions is an important component of ecologisation of agro-technologies and formation of sustainable agro-ecosystems.

Materials and methods. The aim of the research was to determine the effectiveness of the use of alternative organic, non-humified types of fertilizers in combination with basic tillage on agrophysical indicators of soil fertility, formation, size and quality of crop yield in the conditions of central Polissya regions of Ukraine.

The research was conducted during 2021-2023 on the experimental field of the Volyn Agricultural Experimental Station, located in the territory of Rokyni settlement, Lutsk district, Volyn region in crop rotation with the following crop rotation: 1. Clover; 2. Winter wheat; 3. Long-haired flax; 4. Oats; 5. Spring rape; 6. Winter rye; 7. Potatoes; 8. Spring barley with sowing of clover.

The scheme of the experiment implied the study of 3 methods of basic cultivation and 4 fertilisation systems.

Tillage method (factor A):

1. Ploughing at 18-20 cm (control);
2. Flat-cutting cultivation at 18-20 cm;
3. Surface cultivation at 10-12 cm.

Fertilization system (factor B):

1. No fertiliser (control);
2. By-products (straw) + N₁₀;
3. Siderate (yellow lupine);
4. Manure 40 tonnes/ha;

The soil of the experimental plot is sod-podzolic sandy loam. The content of arable layer of soil is characterized by the following agrochemical indicators: humus content – 1,04-1,05%, pH – salt extract – 4,1-5,7, mobile forms of phosphorus (according to Chirikov) – 17,3-19,5, potassium (according to Chirikov) – 7,8-9,6, alkaline-hydrolysable nitrogen (according to Kornfield) – 6,4-8,4 mg per 100 g of absolutely dry soil.

Manure and alternative types of organic fertilizers were earned by main cultivation of the soil, with pre-

liminary disking, according to the scheme of the experiment. Yellow lupine of Yantar variety was used as a siderate.

The area of sowing plot – 50 m², accounting plot - 35 m². Repetition in the experiment is threefold, placement of plots is systematized.

Results of a research. Soil physical properties determine mineralogical, granules and chemical composition, organic matter content, cation ratio in the soil-absorbing complex, type of plants growing in the census, etc.

Cultivated plants grow and develop well only under favorable soil physical parameters, which are regulated by soil cultivation. With the onset of physical ripeness, the optimal physical state of the soil is reached by crumbling.

Because of rational soil tillage, optimal conditions for growth and development of crops are created. It improves physical properties of soil, its thermal, air, water and nutrient regimes; destroys weeds, pathogens and pests of agricultural crops; protects the soil from water and wind erosion; ensures the incorporation of fertilizers and seeds into the soil at the optimum depth, activates microbiological processes, etc.

Granulomeres composition, moisture, cultivation methods and depth, and crops grown influence specific weight of soil. Without cultivation, the density of the structure under the influence of gravity and other factors reaches a certain value, which is usually called equilibrium density [5]. The equilibrium density varies within significant limits, depends on the degree of cultivation, and is an indicator of soil fertility.

Soil compaction also occurs by heavy agricultural machines, tractors and vehicles with specific pressure exceeding 0.8 kg/cm², insufficient depth of loosening, tillage with excessive moisture, insufficient application of organic matter to the soil, unbalanced mineral fertilizers, etc. [7].

According to the results of our research, the method of basic soil cultivation had practically no effect on the specific weight of soil, only had a significant tendency to decrease (Fig. 1).

Porosity, as well as density of structure, are inter-related objective indicators of agrophysical properties and ecological state of soil. The best conditions for soil microflora activity and crop productivity are formed at the ratio of soil solid phase and pores within 50%. At such borehole ratio, optimal conditions for water and air regimes of soil are formed [9].

Figure 1. Specific gravity of 0-30 cm soil layer depending on the method of main cultivation and alternative types of fertilizers, g/cm³ (average for 2021-2023).

According to the variants of the method of basic tillage, the total pore space varied from 52.2 to 60.9 % (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Porosity of 0-30 cm soil layer depending on main tillage and alternative fertilisers, % (average for 2021-2023).

In the variants of flat-cut tillage and disking, compared to ploughing, the soil looseness did not increase significantly.

Thus, these and other factors had a significant impact on crop productivity. Despite the increase in weediness, crop productivity increased with the application of no-tillage tillage methods, the effectiveness of which is statistically reliable.

Yield of field crops is an integral indicator of the influence of the system of methods to optimise the conditions of their cultivation. This fully applies to the elements of winter wheat cultivation technology. Biological features of the variety, plant density and duration of vegetation period and choice of a predecessor, soil

cultivation methods, fertilizer system and degree of plant protection from harmful organisms are determinant in the formation of yield.

To realize the potential productivity of agricultural crops, rational soil tillage is of great importance. With the help of tillage, it is possible to regulate soil processes that occur in the arable layer of soil and contribute to the accumulation of sufficient moisture in the zone of the main mass of roots, as well as nutrient and air-thermal regimes.

Actual crop yields depending on the experimental elements of cultivation technology are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Crop yields depending on basic tillage and alternative fertilizers, t/ha (average for 2021-2023)

Basic tillage	Fertiliser system	Agricultural crops			
		Winter wheat	Winter rye	Spring barley	Potatoes
Ploughing at 18-20 cm (control)	No fertiliser (control)	2,9	2,2	1,9	15,8
	By-products (straw) + N ₁₀	3,2	2,5	2,4	18,5
	Siderate (yellow lupine)	3,5	2,8	2,6	18,8
	Manure 40 tonnes/ha	3,7	2,9	2,8	21,9
Flat-cutting cultivation at 18-20 cm	No fertiliser (control)	3,4	2,6	2,1	17,1
	By-products (straw) + N ₁₀	3,5	2,8	2,6	18,8
	Siderate (yellow lupine)	3,6	3,2	2,9	21,8
	Manure 40 tonnes/ha	3,9	3,6	3,4	25,9
Surface cultivation at 10-12 cm	No fertiliser (control)	3,6	2,8	2,3	17,9
	By-products (straw) + N ₁₀	3,7	2,9	2,7	18,9
	Siderate (yellow lupine)	3,9	3,2	3,4	22,4
	Manure 40 tonnes/ha	4,2	3,7	3,5	26,2

Conclusions. The conducted research on the effectiveness of different types of organic fertilizers and methods of soil tillage in the cultivation of agricultural crops has shown that alternative types of organic fertilizers in combination with no-tillage tillage contribute to increasing their productivity, and provide an opportunity to increase the fertility of light grey forest soils, in combination with other factors.

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